

Figure 4: Paired guide RNA CRISPR-Cas9 genome editing enables NKG2A deletion in primary NK cells.

(a) Schematic representation of the paired guide CRISPR-Cas9 system used to obtain NKG2A-deficient NK cells and the observed genome edits for the combined guides. (b) Genomic indels were quantified by TIDE after sanger sequencing of genomic DNA samples and are shown as percentage of the total reads. N.A. not assigned. (c) NKG2A expression was measured by flow cytometry 4 days after electroploration of primary NK cells with CRISPR-Cas9 RNPs containing gRNAs targeting NKG2A locus. Either one gRNA or a combination of two guides was used in the RNP complex formation (n = 6 or 7 donors \pm SD of the mean). (d) Protein expression levels of different NK-cell surface markers by flow cytometry one week after electroploration with -CTR or NKG2A RNPs (mean \pm SD from at least 6 donors is shown), and after 4h coculture with 721.221 cells at E:T ratio = 1:1 (e). Shown is the mean of at least 6 donors \pm SD. (f) Flow cytometry-based cytotoxicity assay of primary NK cells after 20h coculture with A-431 and Capan-2 (n = 4 donors) cell lines. (g) IFN γ was measured by ELISA from supernatants of cocultures of gene-edited primary NK cells with the indicated cell lines. (Shown is the mean of at least 8 donors \pm SD). Statistical comparisons were performed using a mixed-effects model with matched donors and Šídák's multiple comparisons test (c-e), or two-way ANOVA with matched donors and Šídák's post-hoc test (f, g). *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.005, ****p < 0.001.